

Summation of Binomial Series and Combinatorial Geometric Progression

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Abstract: This paper presents the summation of binomial series and combinatorial geometric series and its theorems, lemmas, and corollaries. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-9]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-9] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series[10-19]. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

Lemma 2. 1: $V_{n-1}^{r+1} + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}$.

Proof. Let us prove this lemma using the combinatorial geometric series.

By substituting $x = 1$ in the combinatorial geometric series $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$, we get

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r (1)^i = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r = V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \cdots + V_{n-1}^r + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}.$$

This is one of the binomial identities based on the combinatorial geometric series.

From the above binomial identity, we get the following result:

$$V_{n-1}^{r+1} + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}, \left(\because \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} V_i^r = V_{n-1}^{r+1} \right).$$

Let us prove the binomial equation $V_{n-1}^{r+1} + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}$.

$$\begin{aligned} V_{n-1}^{r+1} + V_n^r &= \frac{n(n+1)(n+2) \cdots (n+r)}{(r+1)!} + \frac{(n+1)(n+2) \cdots (n+r)}{r!} \\ &= \frac{(n+1)(n+2) \cdots (n+r)}{r!} \left(\frac{n}{r+1} + 1 \right) = \\ &= \frac{(n+1)(n+2) \cdots (n+r)}{r!} \left(\frac{n+r+1}{r+1} \right). \\ V_{n-1}^{r+1} + V_n^r &= \frac{(n+1)(n+2) \cdots (n+r)(n+r+1)}{(r+1)!} = V_n^{r+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the lemma is proved.

3. Theorem on Binomial Series

Theorem 3.1: $V_0^n \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i + V_1^{n-1} \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} 2^i + V_2^{n-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n-3} 2^i + \cdots + 3V_{n-2}^2 + V_{n-1}^1 = 3^n - 2^n$.

Proof. Let us prove this theorem using the following binomial series and its results.

If $x = 1$ and $y = 1$ in $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} x^i y^{n-i} = (x+y)^n$, then $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n$. (1)

Also, if $x = 1$ and $y = 2$ in the binomial series, then $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} 2^{n-i} = 3^n$. (2)

From (1) and (2), we get $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} (2^{n-i} - 1) = 3^n - 2^n$, i.e. $V_0^n (2^n - 1) + V_1^{n-1} (2^{n-1} - 1) + V_2^{n-2} (2^{n-2} - 1) + V_3^{n-3} (2^{n-3} - 1) + \cdots + V_{n-3}^3 (2^3 - 1) + V_{n-2}^2 (2^2 - 1) + V_{n-1}^1 (2^1 - 1) = 3^n - 2^n$.

From this expression, we conclude that

$$V_0^n \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i + V_1^{n-1} \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} 2^i + V_2^{n-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n-3} 2^i + \cdots + 7V_{n-3}^3 + 3V_{n-2}^2 + V_{n-1}^1 = 3^n - 2^n,$$

where $\sum_{i=0}^n 2^i = 2^{n+1} - 1$.

Hence, theorem is proved.

Corollary 3.1: $V_1^{n-1} + 3V_2^{n-2} + \cdots + V_{n-2}^2 \sum_{i=0}^{n-3} 2^i + V_{n-1}^1 \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} 2^i + V_n^0 \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i = 3^n - 2^n$.

Proof. Let us prove this corollary using the following binomial series and its results.

If $x = 1$ and $y = 1$ in $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} x^i y^{n-1} = (x + y)^n$, then $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n$. (1)

Also, if $x = 2$ and $y = 1$ in the binomial series, then $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} 2^i = 3^n$. (2)

Like theorem 3.1, by simplifying (1) and (2), we conclude that

$$V_1^{n-1} + 3V_2^{n-2} + 7V_3^{n-3} + \dots + V_{n-2}^2 \sum_{i=0}^{n-3} 2^i + V_{n-1}^1 \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} 2^i + V_n^0 \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i = 3^n - 2^n$$

Hence, Corollary is proved.

Theorem 3.2: $V_1^{n-1} \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} 2^i + V_2^{n-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n-3} 2^i + \dots + 3V_{n-2}^2 + V_{n-1}^1 = 2 \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 3^i - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i \right)$

Proof. Let us prove this using Theorem 3.1 as follows:

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i + V_1^{n-1} \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} 2^i + V_2^{n-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n-3} 2^i + \dots + 3V_{n-2}^2 + V_{n-1}^1 = 3^n - 2^n + 1 - 1 (\because V_0^n = 1)$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i + V_1^{n-1} \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} 2^i + V_2^{n-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n-3} 2^i + \dots + 3V_{n-2}^2 + V_{n-1}^1 = \frac{2(3^n - 1)}{2} - (2^n - 1)$$

$$\Rightarrow +V_1^{n-1} \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} 2^i + V_2^{n-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n-3} 2^i + \dots + 3V_{n-2}^2 + V_{n-1}^1 = \frac{2(3^n - 1)}{2} - (2^n - 1) - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i$$

$$\therefore V_1^{n-1} \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} 2^i + V_2^{n-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n-3} 2^i + \dots + 7V_{n-3}^3 + 3V_{n-2}^2 + V_{n-1}^1 = 2 \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 3^i - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i \right),$$

where $\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i = 2^n - 1$ and $\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 3^i = \frac{3^n - 1}{2}$.

Hence, theorem is proved.

Corollary 3.2: $V_1^{n-1} + 3V_2^{n-2} + \dots + V_{n-2}^2 \sum_{i=0}^{n-3} 2^i + V_{n-1}^1 \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} 2^i = 2 \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 3^i - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i \right)$.

This is constituted using the Corollary 3.1.

4. Conclusion

In this article, summation of binomial series and combinatorial geometric series and its theorems, lemmas, and corollaries were built using basic ideas. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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